

Evolution-based Feature Selection for Predicting Dissolved Oxygen Concentrations in Lakes (Appendix)

Runlong Yu¹, Robert Ladwig², Xiang Xu³, Peijun Zhu⁴, Paul C. Hanson⁵,
Yiqun Xie⁶, and Xiaowei Jia¹(✉)

¹ University of Pittsburgh, Pittsburgh, USA

² Aarhus University, Aarhus, Denmark

³ University of Science and Technology of China, Hefei, China

⁴ Georgia Institute of Technology, Atlanta, USA

⁵ University of Wisconsin-Madison, Madison, USA

⁶ University of Maryland, College Park, USA

ruy59,xiaowei@pitt.edu, rladwig@ecos.au.dk, demon@mail.ustc.edu.cn,
zpj@gatech.edu, pchanson@wisc.edu, xie@umd.edu

A Operations for Feature Pair Interactions

As the fundamental components in feature interaction, operations are functions where two individual features are converted into an interaction. For the sake of simplicity, we adopt four representative operations as candidate operations to present instantiations of MCES, i.e., $\mathbf{g} = \{\oplus, \otimes, \boxplus, \boxtimes\}$, which are highly used in previous work [3,8,5,9]. These operations (Fig. 1) are described as:

- **Element-wise sum** (\oplus): It takes two input vectors of dimension $|\mathbf{f}|$ and outputs a vector of dimension $|\mathbf{f}|$ that contains their element-wise sum.
- **Element-wise product** (\otimes): It takes two input vectors of dimension $|\mathbf{f}|$ and outputs a vector of dimension $|\mathbf{f}|$ that contains their element-wise product.
- **Concatenation & feed-forward layer** (\boxtimes): It concatenates two input vectors of dimension $|\mathbf{f}|$, and processes them through a feed-forward layer with ReLU activation to reduce the dimension of the output vector to $|\mathbf{f}|$.
- **Element-wise product & feed-forward layer** (\boxplus): It takes two input vectors of dimension $|\mathbf{f}|$, passes their element-wise product through a feed-forward layer with ReLU activation to output a vector of dimension $|\mathbf{f}|$.

B Metabolic Process-based Model

We introduce a metabolic process-based model to generate simulated labels [4]. Our study focuses on changes in ecosystem-scale metabolic fluxes in lakes that stratify (a vertical density difference over 0.05 kg/m^3 between surface and bottom layers, and the presence of a thermocline). These lakes largely adhere to the vertical one-dimensional model assumption [1,7,2], which posits a more pronounced density gradient vertically than horizontally. During stratification, we

Fig. 1. Candidate operations to interact on feature pairs.

simplify the water column into two mixed volumes: the upper epilimnion and the lower hypolimnion, treating the thermocline depth as a dividing barrier between both volumes. Our model primarily focuses on metabolic dynamics during warmer periods, excluding inverse stratification periods in ice-covered winters. This is due to the scarce availability of under-ice DO data and the heightened significance of abiotic-biotic interactions in warmer conditions. For simplicity, we represent the direct flux features that either augment or diminish DO concentrations as F within our metabolic process-based model. Upon obtaining observed DO data, we generate posterior estimates for the process-based model to ascertain F effectively [4].

We integrate information from a hydrodynamic lake model into a metabolism model to study each lake. By constructing a time series of temperatures and volumes for both the epilimnion and hypolimnion, these features are utilized in our process-based metabolism model to simulate DO concentrations and their respective fluxes. Our model simplifies the ordinary differential DO equation for each layer into a discrete, first-order linear solution using an explicit forward Euler scheme with a daily timestep. During stratified conditions, we calculate the DO concentrations over time in the epilimnion as:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{y}_{t+1}^{\text{epi}} = & \left(\tilde{y}_t^{\text{epi}} + \left(F_t^{\text{ATM}} + F_t^{\text{NEP,epi}} \pm F_t^{\text{ENT,epi}} \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. \pm F_t^{\text{DIF,epi}} \right) \times \Delta t \right) \times \frac{V_t^{\text{epi}}}{V_{t+1}^{\text{epi}}}, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where \tilde{y}_t^{epi} denotes the simulated DO concentration in the epilimnion at time t , as estimated by this metabolic process-based model, V_t^{epi} indicates the volume of this epilimnion at time t , F represents the flux features: In the epilimnion it comprises atmospheric exchange (F^{ATM}), net ecosystem production in the epilimnion ($F^{\text{NEP,epi}}$), DO entrainment from or into the hypolimnion by turbulent flow ($F^{\text{ENT,epi}}$), and the diffusive DO flux between layers ($F^{\text{DIF,epi}}$).

The same metabolic process applies to the hypolimnion, where the flux features F to DO concentrations over time in the hypolimnion are net ecosystem production ($F^{\text{NEP,hyp}}$), mineralization through sediment oxygen demand

(F^{SED}), DO entrainment into or from the epilimnion by turbulent flow ($F^{\text{ENT,hyp}}$), and the diffusive DO flux between layers ($F^{\text{DIF,hyp}}$):

$$\tilde{y}_{t+1}^{\text{hyp}} = \left(\tilde{y}_t^{\text{hyp}} + \left(F_t^{\text{NEP,hyp}} - F_t^{\text{SED}} \pm F_t^{\text{ENT,hyp}} \pm F_t^{\text{DIF,hyp}} \right) \times \Delta t \right) \times \frac{V_t^{\text{hyp}}}{V_{t+1}^{\text{hyp}}}. \quad (2)$$

where \tilde{y}_t^{hyp} denotes the simulated DO concentration in the hypolimnion at time t , V_t^{hyp} indicates the volume of the hypolimnion at time t .

C Features for DO Concentration Prediction

The dataset utilized includes around 5.58 million daily records, each with 39 fields of phenological features such as morphometric, flux data, weather conditions, trophic states, and land use details. Observed DO data were sourced from the Water Quality Portal (WQP). Lake residence time was taken from the HydroLAKES. Trophic state probabilities (eutrophic, oligotrophic, dystrophic) were from the dataset [6]. Land use proportions of each lake’s watershed were taken from the National Land Cover Database (NLCD). An account of these features is available in Table 1.

D Visualization of Gene Maps

To demonstrate the model’s evolutionary process and how feature interactions adapt across different lake types and tasks, we visualize the model’s **gene maps**. Adopting an encoding where $\oplus = 0$, $\otimes = 1$, $\boxplus = 2$, $\boxtimes = 3$, we can diagnose the model’s fitness as a symmetric matrix. Distinct colors are allocated to each operation, creating a vibrant gene map where each gene symbolizes an interaction; like red “0”, green “1”, yellow “2”, and blue “3”. For example, a green “1” within the “**depth** \times **area**” block signifies that the element-wise product \otimes is identified as the optimal operation for “**depth**” to interact with “**area**”. The intensity of the colors on the gene map is directly correlated with the relevance of the interactions, with darker hues denoting higher relevance and lighter ones suggesting lesser importance. Individual features are also visually encoded as single-hued bars. Interactions deemed irrelevant, with their relevance parameters reduced to 0, are excluded, leaving their corresponding genes depicted in white “-1”. In Fig. 2, we present gene maps for all lake types and tasks, using end-of-training data to highlight relevant feature interactions for DO concentration prediction.

E Impact of Selected Feature Interactions

As depicted in Figure 3, we evaluate the impact of feature interactions identified by the MCES. By adjusting the RDA optimizer’s parameters, we consistently

Fig. 2. Visualization of gene maps highlighting top relevant feature interactions across different lake types and tasks.

Fig. 3. Feature interaction sparsity impact.

choose a sparser set of feature interactions, accepting a trade-off in accuracy, illustrated by the blue trend line for MCES. Simultaneously, a random strategy is applied for comparative purposes, where operations for feature interactions are allocated at random, and some interactions are arbitrarily removed as sparsity intensifies, as depicted by the red trend line. The gene map showcased at a feature interaction sparsity level around 0.5 offers insight into the model’s structure under reduced complexity.

References

- Hipsey, M.R., Bruce, L.C., Boon, C., Busch, B., Carey, C.C., Hamilton, D.P., Hanson, P.C., Read, J.S., de Sousa, E., Weber, M., et al.: A general lake model (glm 3.0) for linking with high-frequency sensor data from the global lake ecological observatory network (gleon). *Geoscientific Model Development* **12**(1), 473–523 (2019)

2. Janssen, A.B., Teurlinckx, S., Beusen, A.H., Huijbregts, M.A., Rost, J., Schipper, A.M., Seelen, L.M., Mooij, W.M., Janse, J.H.: Pclake+: A process-based ecological model to assess the trophic state of stratified and non-stratified freshwater lakes worldwide. *Ecological modelling* **396**, 23–32 (2019)
3. Khawar, F., Hang, X., Tang, R., Liu, B., Li, Z., He, X.: Autofeature: Searching for feature interactions and their architectures for click-through rate prediction. In: *ACM International Conference on Information and Knowledge Management (CIKM)*. pp. 625–634 (2020)
4. Ladwig, R., Appling, A.P., Delany, A., Dugan, H.A., Gao, Q., Lottig, N., Stachelek, J., Hanson, P.C.: Long-term change in metabolism phenology in north temperate lakes. *Limnology and Oceanography* **67**(7), 1502–1521 (2022)
5. Liu, B., Xue, N., Guo, H., Tang, R., Zafeiriou, S., He, X., Li, Z.: Autogroup: Automatic feature grouping for modelling explicit high-order feature interactions in ctr prediction. In: *Proceedings of the 43rd international ACM SIGIR conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval (SIGIR)*. pp. 199–208 (2020)
6. Meyer, M.F., Topp, S.N., King, T.V., Ladwig, R., Pilla, R.M., Dugan, H.A., Eggleston, J.R., Hampton, S.E., Leech, D.M., Oleksy, I.A., et al.: National-scale remotely sensed lake trophic state from 1984 through 2020. *Scientific Data* **11**(1), 77 (2024)
7. Nielsen, A., Bolding, K., Hu, F., Trolle, D.: An open source qgis-based workflow for model application and experimentation with aquatic ecosystems. *Environmental Modelling & Software* **95**, 358–364 (2017)
8. Song, Q., Cheng, D., Zhou, H., Yang, J., Tian, Y., Hu, X.: Towards automated neural interaction discovery for click-through rate prediction. In: *Proceedings of the 26th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery & Data Mining (KDD)*. pp. 945–955 (2020)
9. Yu, R., Xu, X., Ye, Y., Liu, Q., Chen, E.: Cognitive evolutionary search to select feature interactions for click-through rate prediction. In: *Proceedings of the 29th ACM SIGKDD Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*. pp. 3151–3161 (2023)

Table 1. Features utilized for DO concentration prediction.

Feature Group	Feature Descriptions
Morphometric & Geographic	<p>depth: Derived maximum lake depth area: Derived maximum lake surface area elev: Derived lake elevation Shore_len: Shore length Vol_total: Lake volume Vol_res: Lake volume residual Vol_src: Lake volume supplement Depth_avg: Average lake depth Dis_avg: Average inflow discharge Res_time: Lake residence time Elevation: Alternative lake elevation Slope_100: Lake slope information Wshd_area: Watershed area</p>
Mass Fluxes	<p>fneq: Net ecosystem production flux fmineral: Mineralisation flux fsed: Net sedimentation flux fatm: Atmospheric exchange flux. fdiff: Diffusion flux fentr_epi: Entrainment flux in the epilimnion fentr_hyp: Entrainment flux in the hypolimnion</p>
Weather Conditions	<p>wind: Derived wind speed airtemp: Derived air temperature</p>
Trophic State	<p>eutro: Derived classification for eutrophic state oligo: Derived classification for oligotrophic state dys: Derived classification for dystrophic state</p>
Watershed Land Use	<p>water: Derived classification proportion for water land use developed: Derived classification proportion for developed land use barren: Derived classification proportion for barren land use forest: Classification proportion for forest land use shrubland: Derived classification proportion for shrubland land use herbaceous: Derived classification proportion for herbaceous land use cultivated: Derived classification proportion for cultivated land use wetlands: Derived classification proportion for wetlands land use</p>
Stratification	<p>sat_hypo: Hypolimnion DO saturation concentration thermocline_dept: Thermocline depth temperature_epi: Epilimnion water temperature temperature_hypo: Hypolimnion water temperature volume_epi: Epilimnion volume volume_hypo: Hypolimnion volume</p>